

Project acronym: EVERSE
 Grant Agreement Number:101129744
 Project full title: European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence
 Call identifier: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01

Milestone 5 : Initial Release of the RSQKit (demonstrator)

Version: 1.0
 Status: Submitted
 Dissemination Level: Public
 Deliverable Type: *DEM*
 Due date of deliverable: 28.02.2025
 Actual submission date: 27.02.2025
 Work Package: WP2 Community-led best practices for developing high-quality research software
 Lead partner for this deliverable: UPM
 Partner(s) contributing: UNIMAN

Main author(s):

Name: Daniel Garijo	UPM
---------------------	-----

Other author(s):

Shoaib Sufi	UNIMAN
Aleksandra Nenadic	UNIMAN
Shraddha Bajare	SKAO
Faruk Diblen	NLeSC
Jason Maassen	NLeSC
Mihail Anton	ELIXIR

Initial release of the RSQKit

The Research Software Quality Kit (RSQKit) contains a collection of tools and guidelines on research software quality that align, adapt, and extend to the specific needs of various research communities. The RSQKit mirrors the EVERSE reference model [1], including sections for:

1. Stating how Research Software is defined (including its life cycle and the three tier model).
2. Explaining what research software quality is.
3. Introducing the quality requirements from different science communities (i.e., ENVRI, ESCAPE, PaNOSC and SSH).
4. Introducing roles associated with research software and their relationship to adopt software quality.
5. Providing guidance on performing different tasks for improving research software quality, such as writing readable code, establishing a version control system, selecting a license or making a software project citable.

The RSQKit integrates outcomes from other EVERSE work packages. For example, the “First collection of existing tools and services usable in the science clusters to assess, curate and improve software quality and FAIRness” [2] are available in the RSQKit at: everse.software/RSQKit/all_tools_and_resources. Specific tools are referenced from task pages, illustrating potential usages of each tool.

Setting up and populating the RSQKit

Setting up the framework/infrastructure and population of RSQKit have gone hand in hand. The infrastructure uses the ELIXIR Toolkit theme (elixir-belgium.github.io/elixir-toolkit-theme/) and is inspired by the approach of the RDMkit (rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/). For initial contributions, guidelines (everse.software/RSQKit/contribution_guidelines) and various page templates have been established. An editorial board (everse.software/RSQKit/editorial_board) has been set up to homogenize existing content and ensure compliance with the established contributing mechanisms. Software experts populated an initial set of common tasks for research software quality under the guidance of the editorial board. Content was prioritised through a series of project meetings and workshops. Figure 1 shows a sample of some of the included tasks regarding research software quality.

Figure 1: A sample of some of the tasks included in the RSQKit to date

The initial release of RSQKit is available at the following URLs:

- The RSQKit website: everse.software/RSQKit/
- Development repository on GitHub: github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware/RSQKit
- Release URL: <https://github.com/EVERSE-ResearchSoftware/RSQKit/releases/tag/v1.0.0>
- Zenodo DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14923573>

Bibliography

- [1] Chue Hong, N., Diblen, F., Garijo, D., Maassen, J., Orfanou, A., Pechlivanis, N., & Psomopoulos, F. (2024). EVERSE RSQkit Reference Framework. Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14204479
- [2] Huste, T., Linnemann, K., Vuillaume, T., Gamgami, A., Bajare, S., Juckeland, G., Bartolini, M., Clarke, A., Garijo, D., Pechlivanis, N., Psomopoulos, F. D3.1 — First collection of existing tools and services usable in the Science clusters to assess, curate and improve software quality and FAIRness. Report.

